

Sorption and separation studies of thorium(IV) in L-valine medium using poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6]

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Abstract : A simple method has been developed for the separation of thorium(IV) in L-valine medium using poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] and column chromatography. The sorption of thorium(IV) was quantitative from 1×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-1} M L-valine. Amongst the various eluents 0.5–8.0 M hydrobromic acid, perchloric acid, hydrochloric acid and 0.5–5.0 M sulfuric acid were found to be efficient eluents for thorium(IV). The capacity of poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] for thorium(IV) was 0.258 mmol/g of crown polymer. Thorium(IV) was separated from number of cations and anions in binary mixtures. Most of the cations and anions showed very high tolerance limit. Selective separation of thorium(IV) was possible from uranium(VI), cerium(III) and lanthanum(III). The method was extended to determine thorium(IV) from geological and industrial samples.

Keywords : Sorption, separation, thorium(IV), L-valine, poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6].

Introduction

The importance of thorium has grown many folds due to increasing application of atomic energy. Therefore, there is an analytical requirement for trace determination of thorium in various types of samples ranging from geological to industrial samples.

Since the discovery, crown ethers have been used extensively in various fields of chemistry but extensively used in the analytical chemistry. The crown ethers are well known reagents which are used for the separation and pre-concentration of metal ions¹. The extraction of actinides is significantly done with crown ethers². Also crown ethers are used as a sorbants in chromatographic techniques^{3–6} like TLC, extraction chromatography-liquid chromatography on columns and gas chromatography.

Polymeric crown ether possesses special features such as high resistance to chemicals, temperature, radiolysis and also to polar solvents. These features shown by poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] have been used for selective cation separation from strong acid matrices^{7,8}. The use of poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] for the study of thorium(IV) has been reported in nitrate medium⁹, picric acid¹⁰ and in

ascorbic acid⁵ medium. The separation of thorium(IV) has been carried out by using different ion exchange resins^{11–16} and polymer supported *o*-vanillinsemicabazone¹⁷ by extraction chromatography. But no attempts were made for the separation of the thorium(IV) from associated elements using amino acid media and column chromatography. This paper describes in detail the sorption study of thorium(IV) using L-valine as a medium on poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6].

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

A Ziess (Germany) spectrophotometer, a digital pH meter (Model LI-120, Elico, India) with glass and calomel electrodes and a digital flame photometer (pI, Model No. 041, India) were used.

A stock solution of thorium(IV) was prepared by dissolving 1.312 g of thorium nitrate hexahydrate (AnalaR grade; BDH, Poole, UK) in 500 ml distilled deionised water. The solution was standardized gravimetrically¹⁸. It was found to contain 1.02 mg/ml of thorium(IV). The diluted solution containing 100 µg/ml of thorium(IV) was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. L-

valine solution (0.1 M) was prepared by dissolving 1.1715 g of L-valine (E. Merck India Limited, Worli, Mumbai) in distilled deionised water and diluted to 100 ml.

Poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] from (Merck, Darmstadt; Germany) was used after screening to 100–200 mesh. 0.5 g of polymer was slurred with distilled, deionised water and poured in to a pyrex glass chromatographic column (20 × 0.8 cm i.d.). The column was used after preconditioning with L-valine solution.

General procedure :

100 µg of thorium(IV) was mixed with L-valine in the concentration range of 1×10^{-6} to 1×10^{-1} M in a total volume of 10 ml. The solution was then passed through a poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] column, preconditioned with the same concentration of L-valine as that of the sample solution, at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min. The column was then washed with the same concentration of L-valine. The adsorbed thorium(IV) was then eluted with different eluting agents (described later) at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min. 5.0 ml fractions were collected and the thorium(IV) content was determined spectrophotometrically with Arsenazo-III at 620 nm¹⁹. The concentration of thorium(IV) was calculated from calibration graph.

Results and discussion

Adsorption of thorium(IV) on poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] as function of L-valine concentration :

Adsorption studies of thorium(IV) were carried from L-valine medium using 100 µg of thorium(IV). The concentration of L-valine was varied from 1×10^{-6} to 1×10^{-1} M. After adsorption, the elution of thorium(IV) was carried out with 3.0 M H₂SO₄. It was found that there was quantitative adsorption of thorium(IV) from 1×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-1} M L-valine. After 1×10^{-4} M L-valine concentration there was decrease in the percentage adsorption of thorium(IV) with decrease in L-valine concentration. L-Valine acts as a counter anion for thorium(IV). It forms an ion pair which is getting sorbed on poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6]. Therefore with decrease in L-valine concentration sorption of thorium(IV) is also decreased. The results of adsorption of thorium(IV) are presented in Table 1. The subsequent adsorption studies on thorium(IV) were carried with 1×10^{-3} M L-valine.

Table 1. Adsorption of thorium(IV) as a function of L-valine concentration

Th ^{IV} , 100 µg/ml; eluent, 3.0 M H ₂ SO ₄	
L-Valine concentration (M)	% Adsorption of Th ^{IV}
1×10^{-1}	100
1×10^{-2}	100
1×10^{-3}	100
1×10^{-4}	100
1×10^{-5}	88 (±0.58)
1×10^{-6}	86 (±0.5)

Effect of pH on sorption of thorium(IV) :

100 µg/ml thorium(IV) was mixed with 1.0 ml of 1×10^{-3} M L-valine and the total volume was made to 10 ml. The pH of the solution was varied from 1.0 to 11.0 and the sorption study of thorium(IV) was carried out in this pH range. The results (Table 2) show that there is 100% adsorption of thorium(IV) at this pH range, which indicates that, there is no effect of pH on the sorption of thorium(IV).

Table 2. Effect of pH on the adsorption of thorium(IV)

pH of the load solution ^a	Adsorption (%)
1	100
2	100
3	100
4	100
5	100
6	100
7	100
8	100
9	100
10	100
11	100

^a1.0 ml thorium(IV), (100 µg/ml) solution + 1.0 ml, 1×10^{-3} M L-valine solution + 8.0 ml deionized water.

Elution studies of thorium(IV) with various eluting agents :

100 µg/ml of thorium(IV) was adsorbed on the poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] column at 1×10^{-3} M L-valine concentration. After adsorption, elution of thorium(IV) was carried out using hydrobromic acid, sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, perchloric acid and acetic acid as eluting agents. The concentrations of eluting agents were varied from 0.5–8.0 M. The elution profile of thorium(IV)

with various eluting agents are shown in Fig. 1. The results showed that thorium(IV) was quantitatively eluted with 0.5–8.0 M hydrobromic acid, 0.5–5.0 M sulfuric acid, 5.0–8.0 M perchloric acid and 5.0–8.0 M hydrochloric acid. Acetic acid was found to be an inefficient

Fig. 1. Elution studies of thorium(IV) with various acids.

eluent for thorium(IV). Further elution studies of thorium(IV) in this work were carried out with 3.0 M hydrobromic acid.

Effect of varying concentration of thorium(IV) :

In order to find out the capacity of the poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6], the concentration of thorium(IV) was varied from 100 µg of thorium(IV)/10 ml of solution. The results showed that the adsorption of thorium(IV) was quantitative

upto 600 µg/10 ml. The extent of adsorption of thorium(IV) decreased with increase in concentration of thorium(IV). The capacity of poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] for thorium(IV) was found to be 0.258 mmol/g of crown polymer.

Separation of thorium(IV) from binary mixtures :

An aliquot of solution containing 100 µg thorium(IV) was mixed with foreign ions and L-valine was added so that its concentration was $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ in a total volume of 10 ml. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ions required to cause $\pm 2\%$ deviation in the recovery of thorium(IV). The solution was passed through a poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] column, preconditioned with $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ L-valine at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min. Subsequently the column was washed with 15 ml of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ L-valine. Various foreign ions were not adsorbed hence passed through the column. The effluent was collected and analyzed for foreign ion content. The tolerance limit of various foreign ions is shown in Table 3. The alkali and alkaline earth metals show very high tolerance limits. Most of the *p*-block and *d*-block cations were not adsorbed and show high tolerance. Amongst the inner transition elements, cerium(III), lanthanum(III) and uranium(VI) were adsorbed quantitatively and their separation from thorium(IV) has been described in multicomponent mixtures. The anions of the inorganic and organic acids showed high tolerance limits except SO_4^{2-} .

Separation of thorium(IV) from multi component mixture :

When mixture containing lithium(I)/beryllium(II)/

Table 3. Separation of thorium(VI) from binary mixtures
Th^{IV} - 100 µg, adsorption - $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ L-valine, eluent - 3.0 M HBr

Ion	Added as	Tol. limit (mg)	Ion	Added as	Tol. limit (mg)
Li ⁺	LiCl	50	Tl ³⁺	Tl(NO ₃) ₃ .3H ₂ O	4
Na ⁺	NaCl	250	La ³⁺	LaCl ₃	1
Rb ⁺	RbCl	30	Ce ³⁺	CeCl ₃ .6H ₂ O	0.5
NH ₄ ⁺	NH ₄ Cl	100	V ⁴⁺	VOSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	5
Mg ²⁺	MgCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	100	Cr ⁶⁺	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇	3
Ca ²⁺	CaCl ₂	20	Mo ⁶⁺	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .4H ₂ O	7
Sr ²⁺	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	20	W ⁶⁺	Na ₂ WO ₄ .4H ₂ O	1
Ba ²⁺	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	5	U ⁶⁺	U(NO ₃) ₂ .6H ₂ O	0.1
Co ²⁺	CoCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	40	Cl ⁻	HCl	5
Ni ²⁺	NiCl ₂ .6H ₂ O	25	Br ⁻	HBr	40
Zn ²⁺	ZnCl ₂	100	ClO ₄ ⁻	HClO ₄	15
Cd ²⁺	(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Cd.2H ₂ O	10	SO ₄ ²⁻	H ₂ SO ₄	0.5
Pb ²⁺	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	5	BO ₃ ³⁻	H ₃ BO ₃	30
Cr ³⁺	Cr(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	3	EDTA	EDTA	10
Fe ³⁺	FeCl ₃	0.1	Citrate	Citric acid	10
Al ³⁺	Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ .16H ₂ O	15			

magnesium(II)/molybdenum(VI), uranium(VI)/cerium(III)/lanthanum(III) and thorium(IV) was passed through poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] column at 1×10^{-3} M L-valine concentration, lithium(I)/beryllium(II)/magnesium(II)/molybdenum(VI) was not adsorbed, whereas, uranium(VI)/cerium(III)/lanthanum(III) and thorium(IV) were adsorbed. The lithium(I)/beryllium(II)/magnesium(II)/molybdenum(VI) content of the effluent was analyzed spectrophotometri-

cally. The adsorbed uranium(VI)/cerium(III)/lanthanum(III) was first eluted with 5.0 M acetic acid and finally thorium(IV) was eluted with 3.0 M hydrobromic acid. The uranium(VI)/cerium(III)/lanthanum(III) and thorium(IV) in the respective effluent were analyzed by spectrophotometrically. Using this method, the separation of lithium(I)/beryllium(II)/magnesium(II)/molybdenum(VI), uranium(VI)/cerium(III)/lanthanum(III) and thorium(IV) mixture was achieved, the results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Separation of thorium(IV) from multi component mixture

No.	Mixutre	Taken (μg)	Found ^a (μg)	Recovery (%)	Adsorption condition	Eluent
1	Li ^I	100	99.33	99.33 (± 0.58)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC ^b
	U ^{VI}	100	98.66	98.66 (± 1.15)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	99.44	99.44 (± 0.48)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
2	Li ^I	100	99.65	99.65 (± 0.57)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	Ce ^{III}	50	49.41	98.83 (± 0.87)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	98.57	98.57 (± 1.44)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
3	Li ^I	100	99.00	99.00 (± 1.00)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	La ^{III}	100	97.33	97.33 (± 1.54)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	99.33	99.33 (± 1.32)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
4	Be ^{II}	100	98.67	98.67 (± 1.15)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	U ^{VI}	100	99.56	100.00 (± 1.32)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	97.87	97.87 (± 1.55)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
5	Be ^{II}	100	98.67	98.67 (± 1.53)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	Ce ^{III}	50	49.51	99.02 (± 1.01)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	98.75	98.75 (± 0.72)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
6	Be ^{II}	100	98.65	98.65 (± 0.80)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	La ^{III}	100	97.33	97.33 (± 1.39)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	99.53	99.53 (± 0.72)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
7	Mg ^{II}	100	99.53	99.53 (± 0.57)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	U ^{VI}	100	98.33	98.33 (± 0.96)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	99.43	99.43 (± 1.00)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
8	Mg ^{II}	100	99.67	99.67 (± 0.57)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	Ce ^{III}	50	49.17	98.33 (± 0.59)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	98.50	98.50 (± 1.00)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
9	Mg ^{II}	100	99.67	99.67 (± 0.69)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	La ^{III}	100	97.33	97.33 (± 1.35)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	99.54	99.54 (± 0.78)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
10	Mo ^{VI}	100	100.00	100.00 (± 1.15)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	U ^{VI}	100	98.87	98.87 (± 0.77)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	100.00	100.00 (± 0.75)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
11	Mo ^{VI}	100	99.87	99.87 (± 0.75)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	Ce ^{III}	50	49.00	98.00 (± 0.77)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	100.00	100.00 (± 0.75)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr
12	Mo ^{VI}	100	100.00	100.00 (± 0.58)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	NAPC
	La ^{III}	100	97.33	97.33 (± 0.78)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	5.0 M acetic acid
	Th ^{IV}	100	100.00	100.00 (± 1.32)	1×10^{-3} M L-valine	3.0 M HBr

^aAverage of triplicate analysis.

^bNAPC - No Adsorption Passing Through the Column.

Determination of thorium(IV) in gas mantle :

Known weight of gas mantle sample was digested with 5.0 ml concentrated sulfuric acid. The solution was evaporated and was extracted with 0.1 M nitric acid. The solution was filtered through Whatmann filter paper number-1 and diluted to 100 ml with distilled deionised water. An aliquot of sample solution was analyzed as per the general procedure and the thorium(IV) content was determined. The amount of thorium(IV) found in gas mantle was 19.76% as against the reported value of 19.8%.

Determination of the thorium in geological sample :

Monazite sand sample was brought into solution as per the procedure described elsewhere²⁰. An aliquot of sample solution was subjected for the determination of thorium(IV) as per the above procedure. The amount of thorium(IV) found in monazite sand was 8.56% as against the reported value of 8.6%.

Conclusion :

Using column chromatographic method and poly[dibenzo-18-crown-6] the separation of thorium(IV) from associated elements in L-valine medium has been achieved. L-Valine is non-toxic and environmentally benign medium. After adsorption of thorium(IV) from 1×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-1} M L-valine it was eluted quantitatively with hydrobromic acid, sulfuric acid, perchloric acid and hydrochloric acid. By using this medium it is possible to separate thorium(IV) from uranium(VI), cerium(III) and lanthanum(III). Also it was possible to separate thorium(IV) from a number of cations in binary as well as from multi component mixtures. The method was extended to the determination of thorium(IV) in gas mantle as well as in the monazite sand sample.

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